

ESTABLISHMENT OF SYSTEMATIC COOPERATION OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN WITH THE WORLD COMMUNITY.

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Annotation. A positive image of the country in the international arena is one of the main means of fulfilling historical tasks such as promoting and protecting national interests, as well as ensuring state welfare, sustainable development and strengthening competitiveness. The article describes the process of establishing systematic cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the World community.

Key words: state image, positive image, international arena, subject of international relations, foreign partnership.

Introduction. Various partner countries and international organizations are paying more attention to Uzbekistan, efforts of foreign partners to establish systematic cooperation with the Republic of Uzbekistan are being strengthened. Interest in Uzbekistan by foreign tourists, business representatives and tourists is increasing.

Analysis and results. It should be noted that a number of measures are being taken to effectively strengthen the positive image of Uzbekistan in the international arena and to ensure the stability of this process. In particular, several laws and by-laws were adopted in order to strengthen the legal framework of this field. Here, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" adopted in a new version in 2019 and the Presidential Decree "On additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" can be highlighted. According to this decree, the task of "promoting tourism products of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the international and domestic tourism markets, strengthening the image of the country as a safe place for travel and recreation" has been strengthened¹. Also, the current situation in the field of tourism in our country was analyzed, "in the future of the state policy in the field of tourism, the tourism sector should take the lead in the complex and rapid development of regions and their infrastructure, solve current socio-economic tasks, increase jobs, ensure the diversification and development of regions, the income of the population, the standard of living and

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикасида туризмни жадал ривожлантиришга оид кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги Фармони, 05.01.2019 йилдаги ПФ-5611-сон. // <https://lex.uz/docs/4143188>

improving the quality and investment attractiveness and image of the country" is emphasized². Carrying out an advertising and information campaign that promotes the image of this legal document in the country and abroad; forming the image of a safe state for recreation; Prospective tasks such as developing a plan of measures for cooperation with foreign companies and agencies, including "M&CSAATCNI" agency, have been defined for forming a positive image of Uzbekistan in foreign countries and promoting tourism potential.

In addition, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 defines the conceptual issues in this regard. In particular, the 98th goal of the Development Strategy is called: "Increasing the effectiveness of information delivery aimed at improving the image of our country in the world community." In it, as priority tasks - preparation and implementation of a set of measures aimed at promoting the image of Uzbekistan on the world stage, effective continuation of disseminating impartial information about the progress of reforms in our country, the processes of democratic renewal of society; Factors such as entering the international information markets, jointly developing mechanisms, means and channels for promoting the positive image of Uzbekistan, developing mutual relations and establishing cooperation with leading foreign mass media in order to implement PR-partnership projects in the international arena are envisaged.

A positive image of the country in the international arena is one of the main means of fulfilling historical tasks such as promoting and protecting national interests, as well as ensuring state welfare, sustainable development and strengthening competitiveness. A positive international image helps to strengthen the country's political and economic potential, its prestige and influence in the world community, serves as one of the main factors that create favorable external conditions for foreign investments, advanced technologies, financial and technical support, the promotion of national exports in world markets, and the expansion of the flow of tourists. does. In this field, a lot of practical work is being done to form a positive image of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the international arena, to strengthen it and actively promote it.

In particular, Uzbekistan, as the most important country in Central Asia, is successfully conducting a multi-vector independent foreign policy. The social and political changes that took place after 2016 directly initiated by the head of

² Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон Республикасида туризмни жадал ривожлантиришга оид қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги Фармони, 05.01.2019 йилдаги ПФ-5611-сон. // <https://lex.uz/docs/4143188>

our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev started a new era in the internal and external life of the country and led to the rise of the international image of Uzbekistan.

In this regard, an analytical article on the modern development of Uzbekistan was published in a special issue of the prestigious "Berliner Telegraph" magazine published in Germany in 2020. The author is the famous German political scientist Matthias Dornfeld. In his material entitled "New image of Uzbekistan: openness and readiness for cooperation", he spoke in detail about the large-scale democratic changes taking place in Uzbekistan, the foreign and regional policy of the republic's leadership.

The article states that Uzbekistan, as the center of Eurasia and the most populous country in Central Asia, has a leading position in regional cooperation. "The leadership of the most populous country in Central Asia has realized the need to take a leading role in regional cooperation. Conflicts with neighboring Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan regarding the supply of water to countries located in the lower reaches of regional rivers, including Uzbekistan, were resolved. Bilateral border crossings were opened, and land and air transport links were restored. "Uzbekistan strives for general economic development, security and stability in the region," the author says³. Also, at the end of this analytical article, he concludes that "Uzbekistan has the potential to become one of the important economic centers in the near future due to its excellent geographical location in the center of the new Silk Road and promising potential of labor resources."

Conclusion. The image of the state is directly related to various ratings and indices recognized at the international level. The fact that our country is increasing in the priority ratings is a practical result of the large-scale reforms that are being carried out in order to improve the living conditions of the population, to ensure openness and transparency in the society. In particular, in 2022, Uzbekistan improved its position in 11 of the 19 international rankings announced in 2021 and considered a priority for itself. For example, in 2022, it increased its position by 4 places in the Global Innovation Index and took 82nd place among 132 countries, in the Competitive Industrial Productivity Index it increased by 5 places and took 89th place among 154 countries, improved by 18 places in the E-Government Development Rating, and took 69th place among 193 countries. .

The decree of President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev dated June 2, 2020 "On improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international ratings and indices and introducing a new mechanism of systematic work with them in state bodies and

³ Neues Bild Usbekistans: Offenheit und Kooperationsbereitschaft. // berliner-telegraph.de

organizations" and "Scientific potential in working with international ratings and indices" dated May 18, 2022 and on measures to ensure the harmony of practical activities" it can be said that the work carried out in this direction in our country has reached a new level.

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